

101034439 - Resolution

Medical Genetic Solutions for RESOLUTE

WP1 – Collection and annotation of SLC human genetics data

D1.5 Completion of data-mining workflow

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Document History

Version	Date	Description
V1.1	09 May 2022	Final version
V2.0	16 Sep 2022	Revised version upon PO feedback (update of section “repository for primary data”)

Abstract

Data mining for all SLCs is based on a reproducible workflow in programming language R. A comprehensive set of genetics and genomics data is collected from different open-source data bases. These cover large scale genome wide experiments (DNA, RNA, protein, and metabolite associations), gene-based and single-variant tests for rare variants, curated and reported data, biomedical literature, allele frequencies, therapeutic areas of interest and annotation. Every database was queried for each of the SLCs and filtered depending on the source and question of interest. The focus for filtering the gathered data lies on missense and loss of function variants which can cause drastic alterations in protein structure/function by single amino acid change. For each database, the SLC family is compiled in a file. The first column contains ENSEMBL stable identifiers for each gene, the variants are reported by chromosomal position and if available by reference SNP cluster identifiers (rsid).

Methods

Overview and description of Data sources

Datasource	Description
Open Targets genetics (https://genetics.opentargets.org/) 25 Nov 2021/ Version 6	Human genetics and genomics data for systematic drug target identification and prioritization; Collects common genetic variants; Includes GWAS Catalog, UKBB, FinnGen
leu open gwas project (https://gwas.mrcieu.ac.uk/) Version 5.9.0	A database of 214,068,546,020 genetic associations from 42,410 GWAS summary datasets; Source for qtl, eqtl, pqtl, mqtl data sets
Genebass (https://genebass.org/) Version 0.7.8-alpha	Source for exome-based association statistics; UKBiobank is the primary source; 281k individuals; 3700 traits; Gene-based and single-variant testing, Aggregates SNV scores in a region
ClinVar (https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/clinvar/) Data freeze 01.02.2022	Archive for human variations and phenotypes with supporting evidence
Genome Aggregation Database (gnomAD) (https://gnomad.broadinstitute.org/) Version 2.1.1	Collection of exome and genome sequencing data from different projects; Includes allele frequencies and other summary statistics
LitVar LitVar - NCBI - NLM - NIH Data freeze 01.02.2022	Retrieval of variant relevant information from the biomedical literature
Uniprot (https://www.uniprot.org/)	Resource of protein sequence and functional information
Orphanet (https://www.orpha.net/) Version 5.52.0 11.04.2022	Portal for rare diseases/human genes/genetic phenotypes
PRIORITY Index (http://pi.well.ox.ac.uk:3010/) Data from PMID: 31253980	Framework to prioritize potential targets; Integrating trait associated GWAS data with genomic features (nearby genes, eQTL, HiC); Disease ontologies and network connectivity; 15000 genes evaluated for 30 immune related traits (e.g., Asthma, Gout)
Ensembl Ensembl genome browser 106 Release 106	Ensembl is a genome browser for vertebrate genomes; Supports research in comparative genomics, evolution, sequence variation, transcriptional regulation, gene annotation, alignments, regulatory function prediction and disease data collection

Workflow:

The workflow was developed according to a questionnaire. For each question a database was queried for each of the SLCs and filtered depending on the source. The focus for filtering the gathered data lies on missense and loss of function variants which can cause drastic alterations in protein structure/function by single amino acid change. The Ensembl database is used for annotation of variants and collection of all available transcripts. Disease/phenotype specific filters from open targets platform classify the SLC roughly into the 24 therapeutic areas. Targets without known drugs are reported with the overall genetic association (≥ 0.3). The overall genetic association score considers genetic associations, somatic mutations, drugs, pathways and systems biology, text mining, RNA expression and animal models. For each database, the data for the SLCs are combined in one file. The first column contains Ensembl stable identifiers for each gene, the variants are reported by chromosomal position and if available rsids.

Are there common missense variants within 2MBp of the target gene showing robust association with a disease/relevant phenotype?

- Retrieve missense variants in Open Targets and IEU

Are there eQTLs for the target gene in any GTEX tissue?

- Retrieve missense variants in Open Targets and IEU

Does the GWAS signal show significant colocalization with an expression?

- Retrieve missense variants in Open Targets

Are there rare variants in the target gene showing consistent linkage in familial disease, or association using a genetic burden test?

- Retrieve Genebase gene-based data

Are there missense variants with single-point associations with the phenotype for continuous or categorical traits?

- Retrieve Genebase variant-level data

Are there curated pathogenic variants reported in Clinvar?

- Retrieve Clinvar/Medgen variants

What number of missense variants with an allele count above five are reported?

- Retrieve gnomad missense variants

Are there variants reported in literature?

- Retrieve LitVar variants

Have variants in the target SLC been studied in-vitro?

- Retrieve Uniprot mutagenesis variants

Are there rare genetic disorders/diseases related to the gene?

- Access Orphanet associations

Is the SLC among the top 150 (out of 15000) genes for 30 immune related traits?

- Access the Pi-Score ranking

Is there evidence of association between the target gene and other metabolites?

- Retrieve missense variants in IEU metabolites

Which transcripts are available for each SLC?

- Retrieve transcripts from Ensembl

Does the SLC have a hit in a therapeutic area of interest?

- Retrieve therapeutic areas of interest and overall association score from open targets: therapeutic area (number of SLCs reported)
- Biological process (22)
- Cancer (22)
- Benign neoplasm (2)
- Cardiovascular (29)
- Visual system (37)
- Endocrine system (45)
- Gastrointestinal (53)
- Genetic familial or congenital (53)
- Hematologic (17)
- Immune system (31)
- Infectious (15)
- Infectious disease or post-infectious disorder (15)

- Integumentary system (33)
- Measurement (213)
- Musculoskeletal or connective tissue (66)
- Nervous system (98)
- Nutritional or metabolic (95)
- Pancreas (26)
- Phenotype (59)
- Psychiatric disorder (39)
- Reproductive system (13)
- Breast (3)
- Respiratory or thoracic (44)
- Urinary system (33)

Results

The gathered data are collected source-wise in csv format.

List of csv files:

- clinvar_phenotypes_all_variants.csv
- genebass_gene_based_test_lof_all_variants.csv
- genebass_gene_based_test_missense_all_variants.csv
- genebass_variant_based_test_all_variants.csv
- gnomad_allele_count_missense_variants.csv
- ieu_open_gwas_eqtl_all_variants.csv
- ieu_open_gwas_phewas_all_variants.csv
- ieu_open_metabolites_all_variants.csv
- ieu_open_proteins_all_variants.csv
- litvar_phenotypes_all_variants.csv
- open_targets_gwas_all_variants.csv
- pi_pipeline.csv
- uniprot_mutagenesis_variants.csv
- all_transcripts.csv

List of 24 therapeutic area of interest files:

- [therapeutic_area]_association_open_targets.csv

Conclusion

The data mining for all SLCs is based on a R-workflow covering large scale genome wide experiments (DNA, RNA, protein, and metabolite associations), gene-based and single-variant tests for rare variants, curated and reported data, biomedical literature, allele frequencies, therapeutic areas, and annotation. A comprehensive set of genomics data with stable identifiers for genes and variants is collected for each member of the SLC family. The workflow is reproducible and provides new associations and variants with each new update of the databases.

Repository for primary data

N/A